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Research Article

**KNOWLEDGE ATTITUDE AND PRACTICE OF CHRONIC
KIDNEY DISEASE AMONG MEDICAL OFFICERS OF
TEACHING HOSPITALS OF LAHORE****¹Dr. Tahira Tayyaba Tariq, ¹Dr. Javeria Mahmood, ²Dr. Sundas Firdos**¹Lahore General Hospital²Benazir Bhutto Hospital Rawalpindi**Abstract:**

Objective: The study was organized to know the information, opinion, and practice of kidney disorders in officers related to medical in various hospitals of Lahore.

Study design: The study is cross sectional.

Place and duration of the study:

Nephrology department, King Edward Medical University, Mayo Hospital, Lahore from 1st Jan 2013 to 31st March 2013.

Methodology: Doctors working in different care centers of different hospitals were also involved in studies e.g. Sir Ganga Ram Hospitals, Service Institute of Medical Sciences, Fatima Memorial Hospitals, and Jinnah Hospital etc. A set of 28 questions is given to every doctor. Every doctor was asked to complete all questions given to him in 10 to 15 minutes at that time. Then doctors are categorized on the basis of KAP scores as poor (<50%), average (51_70%) and good (>70%).

Result: According to the criteria selected, one hundred eighty five doctors were selected who fulfill the requirements. The study of nephrology is important but 134(62.5%) doctors were those who had never studied about nephrology in their graduation. Some doctors had some information but most of them did not know anything about the methods of nephrology. Most of the doctors know that nephrology is a medical disease related to kidneys which was important in a way of statistics. Many doctors had a point of view that

Nephrological services are not enough in their hospitals. More than 90 percent doctors think that kidney diseases should be taught in MBBS syllabus to the medical students. They also want separate departments of nephrology. Most of the doctors did not know how to manage hyperkalemia (high potassium level in blood). Most of the doctors know that ACE inhibitors are used in different diseases like hypertension and nephropathy. About 90 percent know about the five stages of CKD. They know that diabetic nephropathy is detected by completely observing the urine of the patient.

Conclusion: Most of the doctors have little information about the neurology. They know very little about diseases of kidneys. Mostly doctors think that they should teach about neurology at their graduation level. They think that their hospitals do not contain enough facilities; there should be separate departments of neurology in the clinics for their gaudiness.

Keywords: Knowledge, Chronic, Kidney Disease, Medical Officers, Teaching Hospitals, Lahore.

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INTRODUCTION:

A KAP survey is a study of specific group of people to collect knowledge on what they know, believe, and do about a specific topic. We can get information about knowledge distance and art or behavioral concepts that may help in understanding the problem or create obstacles of that specific topic. Such types of surveys are helpful for health care centers to make syllabus for medical students and about the care and proper treatment of the patients. In Western countries, according to these surveys, people still have little information about the clinical gaudiness and suggestions. According to published reports in USA, there are about 35 to 54.7% non-nephrology specialist have enough knowledge about CDK. According to Israni and his companions, Agrawal at el., and Charles at el., 35% non-nephrology doctors, 54% family doctors, and 54.7 % of non-nephrology specialists doctors had appropriate knowledge respectively. Boulware and his companions compare the family and non-nephrology physicians, they identified 59% and 78% presence of CDK respectively.

In Pakistan pre dialysis is given to the patients because in Pakistan there are very few numbers of nephrologists. Unsterilized equipments are used that's why patients are not recovered soon and died. In Pakistan little data is available about the knowledge and information of doctors about the kidney diseases. A study was organized by Shaista TZ who evaluates knowledge between inhabitant and councilor. It was a single stand study. Another study was arranged by S Yaqoob et al. He evaluates information between family doctors. But still multicentre study was not arranged for residents. In Pakistan neurology is ignored and progress in this field of medicine is slow. Due to this reason professional doctors don't have enough knowledge about this field. That's why this study is organized to check the awareness and information of doctors of clinical hospitals of Lahore about CDK diseases.

OBJECTIVE:

The main objective of the study is to detect the awareness, attitude and clinical practice of doctors about the nephrological disorders working in different tertiary hospitals.

SUBJECTS AND METHODS:

Doctors which are working in different hospitals of kidney diseases such as Mayo hospital, Sir Ganga Ram Hospital, Service Institute of Medical Sciences, Fatima Memorial Hospital, Lahore General Hospital, Shalimar Hospital, and Jinnah Hospital of Lahore are added in studies. Only doctors related to nephrology

were added in the studies, all other fields were excluded from the studies. A questionnaire was made by special neurologists and it was given to each doctor. Questionnaire consists of 28 questions. The questionnaire comprises of three parts including knowledge, attitude and practice. Questions are related to serious kidney disorders according to The National Kidney Disease Outcome Quality Initiative (NKFKDOQI) guidance. The things identified by doctors were not published. They were kept as secrete studies. According to the performance doctors were categorized as poor (<50%), average (51-70%) and good (>70%).

STATISTICAL ANALYSIS:

After that data is properly checked. The data is assessed by standard SPSS software version -17 for statistical analysis. The continues variables are shown by mean+SD. ANOVA is used to detect the gap between knowledge, attitude and practice's values less than 0.05 was supposed important crude knowledge score, (0.9), attitude (0-5) and practice (0-14) was standard in relation to hundred. Relation between different terms was identified by correlation.

RESULTS:

The doctors who fulfill the requirement of criteria and take part in studies were one hundred and eighty five. There were 131 male doctors and 54 female doctors who participated in studies. Doctors who take part in the study belongs to different hospitals of Lahore i.e. Mayo Hospital 45, LGH 13, SGRH 21, FMH 17, JHL 30, SH 21, SIMS 30. Doctors worked in the hospitals for about 29 weeks. The number of good doctors was less according to the survey. Mostly doctors were categorized as poor and average according to the survey results which given in table 1. The questions asked by doctors and their answers to those questions are given in the table number 2. In this study majority of the doctors were those who never studies nephrology in their graduation which was important according to the statistics. Some doctors know a little bit about the procedures used in nephrology, others did not know at all. However all the doctors know that nephrology belongs to the medical but not surgical disorders of kidneys. Most of the doctors 135 are point of view that there are insufficient facilities about nephrology in their hospitals. More than 90% doctors want to study about nephrological disorders in their MBBS course. They also wants to have separate departments about kidney diseases in their hospitals which was important statistically. Mostly doctors did not had an idea about the about the renal biopsy till now and they did not had an idea how to deal with the hyperkalemia. About 90 percent doctors had information about the five

stages of CDK and Diabetic Nephropathy. Most of the doctors know that urine detection helps them in identification of diabetic nephropathy so they use

ACE inhibitors in hypertension and diabetic nephropathy.

Table:1
Numbers of average, poor and good doctors according to the KAP survey:

Serial no.	Parameter	Numbers in %	P value
1.	Knowledge: Poor Average Good	11.9% 69.7% 18.4%	0.000*
2.	Attitude: Poor Average Good	1.6% 5.4% 92.4%	0.000*
3.	Practice: Poor Average Good	15.7% 50.8% 33.5%	0.000*

Table No: 2
Important questions asked by doctors during study and their answers:

Serial no.	Question asked by doctors	Response by doctors	P value
1.	Have you taught about Nephrology in your curriculum?	a. Taught well 1.4% b. Somewhat taught 29.4% c. Do not taught 62.6%	0.000*
2.	Do you know about procedures done in Nephrology?	a. Know well 2.3% b. Somewhat know 5% c. Do not know 66.8%	0.000*
3.	Does Nephrology deals with medical aspects of kidney?	a. Yes 97.2% b. No 1.4%	0.000*
4.	Do you know about Hemodialysis?	a. Know well 3.7% b. Somewhat know 29.4% c. Do not show 63.6%	0.000*
5.	Does Nephrology deals with surgical diseases of kidney?	a. Yes 25.2% b. No 73.4%	0.000*
6.	Do you think Nephrology services are sufficient in your hospitals?	a. Yes 34.1% b. 64.5%	0.000*
7.	Should Nephrology be taught during MBBS syllabus?	a. Yes 94.4% b. 4.2%	0.000*
8.	Should Nephrology rotation be done in House job?	a. Yes 75.2% b. No 23.4%	0.000*
9.	Should separate Nephrology ward be established?	a. Yes 98.6% b. 9.8%	0.000*
10.	Have you seen renal biopsy until now?	a. Yes 34.1% b. No 64.5%	0.000*

11.	Do you know management of hyperkalemia?	a. Know well 21% b. Somewhat know 71.1% c. Do not know 19.1%	0.000*
12.	How many stages of CDK are there?	a. 3 10% b. 5 89.1%	0.000*
13.	How many stages of Diabetic Nephrology?	a. 3 25.1% b. 5 74.9%	0.000*
14.	Is ACE inhibitor a first choice drug for Hypertension?	a. Yes 63.0% b. No 37%	0.000*
15.	Does Urine complete examination help in early detection of CKD?	a. Yes 87.7% b. No 12.3%	0.000*
16.	Creatinine Clearance is more important than Serum Creatinine?		0.000*
17.	Are ACE inhibitors a first choice of drugs in Diabetes Mellitus?		0.000*

DISCUSSION:

The knowledge gained by a community of that area helps in their understanding about this disease. Attitude means the opinion of an individual towards an issue, thing or object, or a person. Practice means the ways through which they express and explain their information and behavior through their actions. KAP survey helps in the detection of knowledge and MO's and PG's related to their practice in hospitals and their attitude towards patients caution and nursing. This study helps to find out the gaps between knowledge and practice. These studies help in guiding the health agencies for making syllabus for undergraduate and postgraduate level. According to the studies and survey results most doctors have poor or average knowledge about nephrology.

They also have less practice. Some other scientists such as Laura C et al make the similar observations. It is very critical situation for health agencies that the kidney diseases are increasing to an alarming extent in Pakistan for the last two years. 15 to 20 percent persons whose age is more than 40 have a reduced estimated GFR according to the local survey results. In Pakistan, there are maximum 150 ESRD patients and in the following years we will have 16,000 ESRD patients in each year. Due to very expensive cure and high spreading of kidney diseases, the government should make policies to create awareness among the common person about this harmful disease.

Most of the doctors have point of view that there are insufficient facilities about kidney disorders in their hospitals and there must be separate departments in

clinics. In Pakistan there is deficiency of institutes for training of postgraduate doctors. There are only two institutes in province Punjab, Sheikh Zayed Hospital Lahore and Pakistan Institute of Medical Sciences, who served for certification in nephrology for more than twenty five years. Two years back, from Lahore to Hyderabad, there is no single department of nephrology and there are no doctors related to kidney disease. Due to which the patients suffered badly. Because there were no kidney hospitals nearby, the patients have to travel a long distance for treatment. This also increase the cost of treatment too. That's why MO's and PG's doctors feel that they should teach about Nephrology in their syllabus. By doing this, we can train doctors for quick detection of kidney diseases among patients. CDK patients are managed by hands during the training and workshops. Due to management of patients by this way decreases the need of kidney physician for this purpose. The doctors involve in studies know very well that nephrology is a medical disease of kidney not a surgical. Doctors have an idea about the domains of two specialties as separate things. This concept is very important. This is different from our previous knowledge which we observed that doctors can not differentiate between specialties and the referral of the kidney patients. This is very essential change. This change comes due to identification and certification of the of kidney departments in different hospitals of Lahore during the previous few years. A college played a very important role in identification of different departments and institutions of nephrology. That was College of Physician and Surgeon. At that time these colleges are not too good because they were in state of progress at that time but

later on they played a very vital role in prevention of kidney disorders. They also provide very good nephrologists by training them in a good and beneficial way. Various methods are used in the field of nephrology for example temporary catheter insertion, renal biopsies, peritoneal dialysis and hemodialysis. Most of the doctors did not know anything about these methods before. Only eight doctors know something about hemodialysis. And one third numbers of doctors had information about renal biopsy.

There is difficulty for these postgraduate doctors in handling and dialysis of the patients when they become consultant after their fellowship programmes. So these patients are managed more betterly in Tehsil and District level hospitals. Government is now providing the dialysis centers for patients in every corner but still there is deficiency of skilled and trained nephrological physicians. Government should also start the training for doctors to improve this field of medicine and for proper treatment of patients suffering from kidney diseases. CKD is linked with many electrolytic disturbances. In nephrology there are few disorders which are extremely life threatening like pulmonary edema hyperkalemia, uremia and pericarditis. Hyperkalemia is an important disorder due to its cardiac events. According to this study, only a few doctors know about the treatment or causes of these diseases. Only 21% doctors know very well about the administration of this disease.

It has also been observed during this study that doctors direct some drugs like ACEI and ARBs to the patient. They did not tell the patients about the harms of these drugs like acute rise in creatinine and hyperkalemia. The follow up of these patients should be done after the first week and first or second month after the treatment of the patient, according to international guideline about this disease. The doctors even did not have an idea which diet contains high level of potassium in it. So patients are present in the hospitals emergencies with ECG changes and even with complete heart block. So it is very necessary to train the doctors about this harmful disease, so they can manage and cure it very efficiently. On the basis of GFR, serious kidney diseases are classified into five stages according to guidelines given by international association of kidney diseases. In this study most of the doctors have information about the serious kidney diseases and diabetic nephropathy. Another report was made by Shaista Tamizzudin having similar observations. According to her observations most of the doctors know about the five stages of kidney disorders. The treatment of kidney

diseases varies with stages so it is important for kidney physicians to have knowledge about the stages of kidney diseases. According to these guidelines AV fistula should be made if the GFR of the patient is less than 20ml/min and the patients should be referred to the nephrologists if they have less than 30ml per minute GFR.

It is important to identify kidney diseases in their early stages. If we observe a person's urine completely it is said to be the poor man renal biopsy. It is very useful for early identification of kidney diseases. Most of the doctors in this study know that urine complete observation is helpful for them to identify the disease. ACE inhibitors are used as a drug of choice for hypertension and diabetic mellitus. 93.3% doctors involve in this study can control the HTN with ACEI. Similar observations were also made by Hermann R et al. According to her observations, 80.1% of the doctor refers ACEI and ARB in hypertension patient with diabetic nephropathy. There is another scientist whose name is S Yaqoob with his companions, made a different observation about the study of GP's. Only 46.1% doctors choose ACEI and ARB as the therapy to cure both blood pressure and proteinuria in order to decrease the progress and spreading of CKD.

According to the K/DOQI provided guideline estimated GFR is the better protective tool recommended than creatinine. Roughly guess GFR is more correct criteria of kidney function than serum creatinine. GFR is used for the both identification and staging of complexity of CKD. Most of the doctors in this study do not know creatinine clearance is more essential than serum creatinine. But it is different from the observation arranged by Varum Agrawal. According to Varum Agrawal 87% of the inhabitants have an information about GFR.

Although this study is very useful in the field of Nephrology but it has some limitations. The main drawback is that the data collected only from Lahore so it gives information only about the doctors working in Lahore. It is not representative data in other cities of the country.

CONCLUSION:

CKD is very harmful and dangerous disease and its complexities cause death of many patients. To prevent this disease, knowledge and information among doctors should be increased. More departments of kidney diseases should be built up to increase the knowledge and awareness among kidney physiologists. KAP analysis should be made after regular intervals to judge the improvements of doctors and create awareness among them.

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